

**Extract from Protocol No. 2
of the Scientific Council Meeting
Institute of Philosophy and Sociology of ANAS
dated April 30, 2024**

Heard: Discussion of the monograph by Senior Research Fellow of the Sociology Department, Doctor of Philosophical Sciences, Associate Professor A.A. Alizade titled “Communal Economy in Azerbaijan in the Mid-20th Century (Historical-Sociological Study)”.

- Resolved:**
1. Recommend the monograph “Communal Economy in Azerbaijan in the Mid-20th Century (Historical-Sociological Study)” by Senior Research Fellow of the Sociology Department, Doctor of Philosophical Sciences, Associate Professor A.A. Alizade for publication.
 2. Approve Professor Hüseyin Qarashov, Doctor of Sociological Sciences, as the scientific editor.

Scientific Secretary: (Signature) **S.A. Hasanova**

Seal: (Official stamp of the Institute)